

Figure S1. A detailed workflow of our Phylogenetic Subgenome Detection (PhyloSD) pipeline highlighting the scripts used in our ‘*Nearest Diploid Species Node*’, ‘*Bootstrapping Refinement*’, and ‘*Subgenome Assignment*’ algorithms. The bioinformatics tools and analyses developed are shown in turquoise color, the outputs of each step in green color, and the two main final outputs of the first/second and third algorithms in violet and red, respectively. Parallel coalescence-based validations for the selection of the optimal diploid skeleton tree and the tested efficiency of the ‘*Subgenome Assignment*’ algorithm are indicated in blue letters.

Figure S2. (a) The optimal *Triticum-Aegilops* diploid skeleton trees obtained through distance-based coalescence analyses with the ASTRAL, STAR and STEAC programs using 259 genes. **(b)** Bidimensional Principal Coordinate Analysis (PCoA) plot constructed from pairwise patristic distances between diploid ortholog and polyploid homeolog tips of the *Triticum-Aegilops* homeologs’ ML tree computed with NTSYS-pc v2.10j. Each homeolog was labelled according to the branch of the skeleton diploid tree where it was grafted to (Figures 2a,b) using the ‘*Nearest Diploid Species Node*’ algorithm. A Minimum Spanning Tree was superimposed on the PCoA. The down-frequency-rank of grafting distributions of each polyploid homeolog-type across 100 bootstrap gene trees (Table S1a) is represented as a colored cluster in solid (1st rank), dashed (2nd rank) and dotted (3rd and 4th ranks) lines. Only the most frequent homeolog-types are shown according to ploidy level. Black lower-case letters in squares indicate groups of homeolog-types. Capital letters indicate the inferred homeolog subgenomes using the *Subgenome Assignment* algorithm (Table 1a, Inferred Subgenomes; Table S1b). Clusters represent bootstrap distributions of homeologs with threshold cut-off values over 10% (Table S1a). Color lower case letters next to clusters indicate the polyploids’ homeolog-types that generated the overlapping distributions. Color codes for taxa and line styles for ranks of homeolog-type frequencies are indicated in the respective charts.

Figure S3. (a) The optimal *Brachypodium* diploid skeleton trees obtained through distance-based coalescence analyses with the ASTRAL, STAR and STEAC programs using 1,877 core transcripts. **(b)** Bidimensional Principal Coordinate Analysis (PCoA) plot constructed from pairwise patristic distances between diploid ortholog and polyploid homeolog tips of the *Brachypodium* homeologs’ ML tree computed with NTSYS-pc v2.10j. Each homeolog was labelled according to the branch of the skeleton

diploid tree where it was grafted to (Figure 3a,b) using the ‘*Nearest Diploid Species Node*’ algorithm. A Minimum Spanning Tree was superimposed on the PCoA. The down-frequency-rank of grafting distributions of each polyploid homeolog-type across 100 bootstrap gene trees (Table S4a) is represented as a colored cluster in solid (1st rank), dashed (2nd rank) and dotted (3rd and 4th ranks) lines. Only the most frequent homeolog-types are shown according to ploidy level. Black lower-case letters in squares indicate groups of homeolog-types. Capital letters indicate the inferred homeolog subgenomes using the *Subgenome Assignment* algorithm (Table 1b, Inferred Subgenomes; Table S4b). Clusters represent bootstrap distributions of homeologs with threshold cut-off values over 10% (Table S4a). Color lower case letters next to clusters indicate the polyploids’ homeolog-types that generated the overlapping distributions. Color codes for taxa and line styles for ranks of homeolog-type frequencies are indicated in the respective charts.

Figure S4. (a) The *Brachypodium* diploid species trees obtained through distance-based coalescence analyses with the ASTRAL, STAR and STEAC programs using 193 orthologous coding sequences (CDS) of the *Brachypodium* (*B. stacei* ABR114, *B. distachyon* Bd21, *B. arbuscula* Barb1, *B. sylvaticum* Ain-1) and outgroup diploid references genomes. (b) *Brachypodium hybridum* ABR113 homeologs’ ML consensus tree based on 160 orthologous CDS (Table S5) with the polyploid homeolog sequences labeled according to the *Nearest Diploid Species Node* algorithm (‘b’ and ‘d’). (c) *Brachypodium hybridum* ABR113 subgenomic ML consensus tree based on 160 orthologous CDS with its homeolog subgenomes labeled according to the *Subgenome Assignment* algorithm (‘B’ and ‘D’). *Oryza sativa* and *Hordeum vulgare* were used as the outgroups. All SH-aLRT/UltraFast Bootstrap supports are 100/100.

Figure S5. (a) *Brachypodium* nuclear diploid skeleton tree based on 322 core transcripts. (b) *Brachypodium* plastid diploid skeleton tree based on 31 plastid transcripts. The values on branches indicate the SH-aLRT/UltraFast Bootstrap supports.

Figure S6. Distribution of the BAC clones derived from chromosomes Bd1-Bd5 of *B. distachyon* ($2n = 10$, $x = 5$) that were comparatively mapped to, respectively, the chromosomes of the (a) diploid *B. arbuscula* ($2n = 18$, $x = 9$), (b) autohexaploid *B. boissieri* ($2n = 48$, $x = 8 + 8 + 8$) and (c) allotetraploid *B. retusum* ($2n = 32$, $x = 8 + 8$). Only one homologue from a pair is shown. The diagrams next to the *Brachypodium* [Bd, Ba (a); Bd, Bb (b); Bd, Bb, Br (c)] chromosomes align the BAC clones to the

homeologous regions (syntenic segments) in the relevant ancestral rice chromosome equivalents Os1-Os12. Black diamonds and dotted lines indicate the hypothetical fusion points of the ancestral rice chromosome equivalents (adapted from IBI 2010). Red dashed lines indicate the chromosomal breakpoints in the Ba-genome chromosomes of *B. arbuscula* (a), Bb-genome chromosomes of *B. boissieri* (b) and Bb- and Br-subgenome chromosomes in *B. retusum* (c) that were found using CCB. Red arrows point to a pericentric inversion that was found on chromosome Bb6 (b, c).

Figure S7. BAC-FISH-based comparative chromosome barcoding with the clones derived from chromosome Bd1 (a) and Bd2 (c) of *B. distachyon* ($2n = 10, x = 5$) mapped to chromosomes Ba2, Ba6 and Ba7 (b) and chromosomes Ba1 and Ba8 (d) of *B. arbuscula* ($2n = 18, x = 9$). Only one homologue from a pair is shown. The colors of the BAC identifiers in the first column indicate the fluorochrome that was used (green, FITC; red, tetramethylrhodamine; yellow [false color], Alexa Fluor 647). The chromosomes were counterstained with DAPI (blue). The colored bars on the left and the BAC identifiers that were assigned to specific clones correspond to those on the cytogenetic maps in Figure S6. BACs Bd1S/1 and Bd1L/14 from Bd1 mapped to chromosome Ba2, probes Bd1S/3 and Bd1L/12 hybridised to Ba6 and probes Bd1S/7-Bd1L/8 to Ba7 (b). BACs Bd2S/1-2 and Bd2L/5-6 from Bd2 mapped to chromosome Ba1, probes Bd2S/3 and Bd2L/4 hybridised to Ba8 (d). Probes Bd1S/1-3-7, Bd1L/8-12-14 from Bd1 and Bd2S/1-2-3, Bd2L/4-5-6 from Bd2 show the chromosomal breakpoints in *B. arbuscula* (b, d) compared to the chromosomal fusion points in *B. distachyon* (a, c). Probes Bd1S/1 + CEN + Bd1L/14 map to chromosome Ba2, whereas probes Bd1S/3 + CEN + Bd1L/12 hybridised to chromosome Ba6 and Bd1S/7 + CEN + Bd1L/8 to chromosome Ba7 (b), thus indicating the presence of two NCF events in the Bd genome of *B. distachyon* that involve three ancestral chromosomes, which were similar to Ba2, Ba6 and Ba7 of the $x = 9$ genome. Probes Bd2S/1 + CEN + Bd2L/6 hybridised to Ba1, whereas probes Bd2S/3 + CEN + Bd2L/4 map to chromosome Bp8 (d), thus indicating the presence of one NCF event in the Bd genome of *B. distachyon* that involved two ancestral chromosomes that were similar to Ba1 and Ba8 of the $x = 9$ genome of *B. arbuscula*.

Figure S8. BAC-FISH-based comparative chromosome barcoding with the clones derived from chromosome Bd3 (a) and Bd4, Bd5 (c) of *B. distachyon* ($2n = 10, x = 5$) mapped to chromosomes Ba4 and Ba3 (b) and chromosomes Ba5 and Ba4 (d) of *B.*

arbuscula ($2n = 18, x = 9$). Only one homologue from a pair is shown. The colors of the BAC identifiers in the first column indicate the fluorochrome that was used (green, FITC; red, tetramethylrhodamine; yellow [false color], Alexa Fluor 647). The chromosomes were counterstained with DAPI (blue). The colored bars on the left and the BAC identifiers that were assigned to specific clones correspond to those on the cytogenetic maps in Figure S6a. BACs Bd3S/1 and Bd3L/10 from Bd3 mapped to chromosome Ba4, probes Bd3S/3-5 and Bd3L/6-7 hybridised to Ba3 (b). BACs Bd4S/1-3-4 and Bd4L/6-8-10 from Bd4 mapped to chromosome Ba5 (d). Probes Bd5S/1 and Bd5L/2 hybridised to Ba9 (d). Probes Bd3S/1-3-5, Bd3L/6-7-10 from Bd3 show the chromosomal breakpoints in *B. arbuscula* (b) compared to the chromosomal fusion points in *B. distachyon* (a). Probes Bd3S/1+ CEN + Bd3L/10 map to chromosome Ba4, whereas probes Bd3S/5 + CEN + Bd3L/6 hybridised to chromosome Ba3, thus indicating the presence of one NCF event in the Bd genome of *B. distachyon* that involved two ancestral chromosomes, which were similar to Ba4 and Ba3 of the $x = 9$ genome. Probes Bd2S/1 + CEN + Bd2L/6 hybridised to Ba1, whereas probes Bd2S/3 + CEN + Bd2L/4 map to chromosome Bp8 (d), thus indicating the presence of one NCF event in the Bd genome of *B. distachyon* that involved two ancestral chromosomes that were similar to Ba1 and Ba8 of *B. arbuscula*.

Figure S9. BAC-FISH-based comparative chromosome barcoding with the clones derived from chromosome Bd1 of (a) *B. distachyon* ($2n = 10, x = 5$) mapped to six Bb2 and six Bb6 chromosomes (b) of autohexaploid *B. boissieri* ($2n = 48, x = 8 + 8 + 8$). Only one homologue from a pair is shown. The colors of the BAC identifiers in the first column indicate the fluorochrome that was used (green, FITC; red, tetramethylrhodamine; yellow [false color], Alexa Fluor 647). The chromosomes were counterstained with DAPI (blue). The colored bars on the left and the BAC identifiers that were assigned to specific clones correspond to those on the cytogenetic maps in Figure S6b. BACs Bd1S/1-2 and Bd1L/13-14 mapped to chromosomes Bb2, probes Bd1S/3-7 and Bd1L/8-12 to Bb6. BAC clones Bd1S/1-3 and Bd1L/12-14 show chromosomal breakpoints in all three subgenomes of Bb compared to the chromosomal fusion points in the genome Bd. Probes Bd1S/1+ CEN + Bd1L/14 map to chromosome Bb2, whereas probes Bd1S/3 + CEN + Bd1L/12 hybridised to chromosome Bb6, thus indicating the presence of one NCF event in the Bd genome of *B. distachyon* that involved two ancestral chromosomes, which were similar to Bb2 and Bb6. Within the

BAC triplet Bd1S/3-5, clones Bd1S/4-5 mapped to the opposite chromosome arm compared to Bd1S/3. Probe triplets Bd1S/5-6-7 were characterised by an inverted arrangement of clones on the long arm of Bb2 compared to the short arm of the chromosome Bd. Comparative mapping of Probe Bd1S/7 + CEN + Bd1L/8 indicated the presence of a pericentric inversion within chromosome Bb6 of *B. boissieri*.

Figure S10. BAC-FISH-based comparative chromosome barcoding with the clones derived from chromosome Bd2 and Bd4 of (a) *B. distachyon* ($2n = 10, x = 5$) mapped to six Bb1 and six Bb8 chromosomes (b) of autohexaploid *B. boissieri* ($2n = 48, x = 8 + 8 + 8$). Only one homologue from a pair is shown. The colors of the BAC identifiers in the first column indicate the fluorochrome that was used (green, FITC; red, tetramethylrhodamine; yellow [false color], Alexa Fluor 647). The chromosomes were counterstained with DAPI (blue). The colored bars on the left and the BAC identifiers that were assigned to specific clones correspond to those on the cytogenetic maps in Figure S6b. BACs Bd2S/1-2 and Bd2L/5-6 mapped to chromosomes Bb1, probes Bd2S/3 and Bd2L/4 to Bb8. BAC clones Bd2S/1-3 and Bd2L/4-6 show chromosomal breakpoints in all three subgenomes of Bb compared to the chromosomal fusion points in the genome Bd. Probes Bd2S/1+ CEN + Bd2L/6 map to chromosome Bb1, whereas probes Bd2S/3 + CEN + Bd2L/4 hybridised to chromosome Bb8, thus indicating the presence of one NCF event in the Bd genome of *B. distachyon* that involve two ancestral chromosomes, which were similar to Bb1 and Bb8. Within the BAC triplet Bd2S/3 + Bd4S/4 + Bd5L/9 and Bd2S/3 + CEN+ Bd4L/6 probes Bd2-derived and Bd4-derived mapped to the opposite arms of the chromosome Bb8 indicating the presence of chromosomal fusion.

Figure S11. BAC-FISH-based comparative chromosome barcoding with the clones derived from chromosome Bd3 of (a) *B. distachyon* ($2n = 10, x = 5$) mapped to six Bb4 and six Bb3 chromosomes (b) of autohexaploid *B. boissieri* ($2n = 48, x = 8 + 8 + 8$). Only one homologue from a pair is shown. The colors of the BAC identifiers in the first column indicate the fluorochrome that was used (green, FITC; red, tetramethylrhodamine; yellow [false color], Alexa Fluor 647). The chromosomes were counterstained with DAPI (blue). The colored bars on the left and the BAC identifiers that were assigned to specific clones correspond to those on the cytogenetic maps in Figure S6b. BACs Bd3S/1-2 and Bd3L/8-10 mapped to chromosomes Bb4, whereas probes Bd3S/3-5 and Bd3L/6-7 mapped to Bb3. BAC clones Bd3S/1-3 and Bd3L/6-8

show chromosomal breakpoints in all three subgenomes Bb compared to the chromosomal fusion points in the genome Bd. Probes Bd3S/1+ CEN + Bd3L/10 map to chromosome Bb4, whereas probes Bd3S/5 + CEN + Bd3L/6 hybridised to chromosome Bb3, thus indicating the presence of one NCF event in the Bd genome of *B. distachyon* that involve two ancestral chromosomes, which were similar to Bb4 and Bb3.

Figure S12. BAC-FISH-based comparative chromosome barcoding with the clones derived from chromosome Bd4 of (a) *B. distachyon* ($2n = 10, x = 5$) mapped to six Bb5 and six Bb8 chromosomes (b) of autohexaploid *B. boissieri* ($2n = 48, x = 8 + 8 + 8$) and from Bd5 of (a) *B. distachyon* mapped to six Bb7 chromosomes (b) of *B. boissieri*. Only one homologue from a pair is shown. The colors of the BAC identifiers in the first column indicate the fluorochrome that was used (green, FITC; red, tetramethylrhodamine; yellow [false color], Alexa Fluor 647). The chromosomes were counterstained with DAPI (blue). The colored bars on the left and the BAC identifiers that were assigned to specific clones correspond to those on the cytogenetic maps in Figure S6b. BACs Bd4S/1-3 and Bd4L/7-10 mapped to chromosomes Bb5, probes Bd4S/4-5 and Bd4L/6 to Bb8. BAC clones Bd4S/3-5 and Bd4L/6-7 show chromosomal breakpoints in all three subgenomes Bb compared to the chromosomal fusion points in the genome Bd. Probes Bd4S/1+ CEN + Bd4L/10 map to chromosome Bb5, whereas probes Bd4S/5 + CEN + Bd4L/6 hybridised to chromosome Bb8, thus indicating the presence of one NCF event in the Bd genome of *B. distachyon* that involve two ancestral chromosomes. Within the BAC triplets, Bd4S/5 + CEN + Bd4L/6 mapped to the same chromosome arm compared to Bd4 of *B. distachyon* and BACs Bd5S/1 and Bd5L/2 mapped to short and long arms of chromosomes Bb7 of *B. boissieri* respectively.

Figure S13. BAC-FISH-based comparative chromosome barcoding with the clones derived from chromosomes Bd1-Bd4 of (a) *B. distachyon* ($2n = 10, x = 5$) mapped to various chromosomes (b) of autohexaploid *B. boissieri* ($2n = 48, x = 8 + 8 + 8$). Only one homologue from a pair is shown. The colors of the BAC identifiers in the first column indicate the fluorochrome that was used (green, FITC; red, tetramethylrhodamine; yellow [false color], Alexa Fluor 647). The chromosomes were counterstained with DAPI (blue). The colored bars on the left and the BAC identifiers that were assigned to specific clones correspond to those on the cytogenetic maps in Figure S6b. Within each BAC triplet, the probes correspond to different ancestral

chromosomes. None of the applied BAC triplets indicate chromosomal fusion or different hybridization pattern among subgenomes.

Figure S14. BAC-FISH-based comparative chromosome barcoding with the clones derived from chromosome Bd1 and Bd3 of (a) *B. distachyon* ($2n = 10, x = 5$) mapped to chromosomes Bb2, Bbr2, Bb6, Br4, Br6 and Br5 (b) of allotetraploid *B. retusum* ($2n = 32, x = 8 + 8$). Only one homologue from a pair is shown. The colors of the BAC identifiers in the first column indicate the fluorochrome that was used (green, FITC; red, tetramethylrhodamine; yellow [false color], Alexa Fluor 647). The chromosomes were counterstained with DAPI (blue). The colored bars on the left and the BAC identifiers that were assigned to specific clones correspond to those on the cytogenetic maps in Figure S6c. BACs Bd1S/1-2 and Bd1L/13-14 mapped to chromosomes Bb2 and Br2. BAC clones Bd1S/3-7 and Bd1L/8-12 mapped to chromosome Bb6, probes Bd1S/3-4 and Bd1L/10-12 hybridised to Br4. Moreover, BACs Bd1S/5-7 mapped to Br6 and Bd1L/8-9 hybridised to Br5. BAC clones Bd1S/1-3, Bd1S/3-5, Bd1S/7 + CEN + Bd1L/8, Bd1L/8-10 and Bd1L/12-14 show chromosomal breakpoints in subgenomes Bb and Br compared to the chromosomal fusion points in the genome Bd. Probes Bd1S/1+ CEN + Bd1L/14 map to chromosomes Bb2 and Br2, whereas probes Bd1S/3 + CEN + Bd1L/12 hybridised to chromosome Bb6 and Br4. Within the BAC triplet Bd1S/3-5, clones Bd1S/4-5 mapped to the opposite chromosome arm of Bb6 compared to probe Bd1S/3. Probe triplets Bd1S/5-6-7 were characterised by an inverted arrangement of clones on the long arm of Bb2 compared to the short arm of the chromosome Bd. Comparative mapping of probes Bd1S/7 + CEN + Bd1L/8 indicating the presence of a pericentric inversion within chromosome Bb6. Within BAC triplet Bd1S/3 + Bd1S/7 + Bd3S/1 probes Bd1S/3 + Bd1S/7 mapped to the same arm of the chromosome Bb6 indicating the presence of chromosomal fusion that involve two ancestral chromosomes, similar to chromosome Bd1 of *B. distachyon*. Moreover, in contrast to *B. distachyon* chromosomes probes Bd1S/3 + Bd3S/1 mapped to the same arm of the chromosome Br4 indicating the presence of chromosomal fusion that involved two ancestral chromosomes.

Figure S15. BAC-FISH-based comparative chromosome barcoding with the clones derived from chromosome Bd2, Bd4 and Bd5 of (a) *B. distachyon* ($2n = 10, x = 5$) mapped to chromosomes Bb1, Br1, Bb8, Br8, Br6 and Br7 (b) of allotetraploid *B. retusum* ($2n = 32, x = 8 + 8$). Only one homologue from a pair is shown. The colors of

the BAC identifiers in the first column indicate the fluorochrome that was used (green, FITC; red, tetramethylrhodamine; yellow [false color], Alexa Fluor 647). The chromosomes were counterstained with DAPI (blue). The colored bars on the left and the BAC identifiers that were assigned to specific clones correspond to those on the cytogenetic maps in Figure S6c. BACs Bd2S/1-2 and Bd2L/5-6 mapped to chromosomes Bb1 and Br1 probes Bd2S/3 and Bd2L/4 to Bb8 and Br8. BAC clones Bd2S/1-3 and Bd2L/4-6 show chromosomal breakpoints in subgenomes Bb and Br compared to the chromosomal fusion points in the genome Bd. Probes Bd2S/1+ CEN + Bd2L/6 map to chromosomes Bb1 and Br1, whereas probes Bd2S/3 + CEN + Bd2L/4 hybridised to chromosomes Bb8 and Br8. Within the BAC triplet Bd2S/3 + Bd4S/4 + Bd5L/2 probes Bd2-derived and Bd4-derived mapped to the opposite arms of the chromosome Bb8 indicating the presence of chromosomal fusion in Bb that differentiate it from genome Br.

Figure S16. BAC-FISH-based comparative chromosome barcoding with the clones derived from chromosome Bd3 of (a) *B. distachyon* ($2n = 10, x = 5$) mapped to chromosomes Bb4, Br4, Bb3 and Br3 (b) of allotetraploid *B. retusum* ($2n = 32, x = 8 + 8$). Only one homologue from a pair is shown. The colors of the BAC identifiers in the first column indicate the fluorochrome that was used (green, FITC; red, tetramethylrhodamine; yellow [false color], Alexa Fluor 647). The chromosomes were counterstained with DAPI (blue). The colored bars on the left and the BAC identifiers that were assigned to specific clones correspond to those on the cytogenetic maps in Figure S6c. BACs Bd3S/1-2 and Bd3L/8-10 mapped to chromosomes Bb4 and Br4, whereas probes Bd3S/3-5 and Bd3L/6-7 mapped to Bb3 and Br3. BAC clones Bd3S/1-3 and Bd3L/6-8 show chromosomal breakpoints in subgenomes Bb and Br compared to the chromosomal fusion points in the genome Bd. Probes Bd3S/1+ CEN + Bd3L/10 map to chromosomes Bb4 and Br4, whereas probes Bd3S/5 + CEN + Bd3L/6 hybridised to chromosomes Bb3 and Br3.

Figure S17. BAC-FISH-based comparative chromosome barcoding with the clones derived from chromosome Bd4 and Bd1 of (a) *B. distachyon* ($2n = 10, x = 5$) mapped to chromosomes Bb5, Br5, Bb6, Br6 and Bb8 (b) of allotetraploid *B. retusum* ($2n = 32, x = 8 + 8$). Only one homologue from a pair is shown. The colors of the BAC identifiers in the first column indicate the fluorochrome that was used (green, FITC; red, tetramethylrhodamine; yellow [false color], Alexa Fluor 647). The chromosomes were

counterstained with DAPI (blue). The colored bars on the left and the BAC identifiers that were assigned to specific clones correspond to those on the cytogenetic maps in Figure S6c. BACs Bd4S/1-3 and Bd4L/7-10 mapped to chromosome Bb5 and probes Bd4S/4 and Bd4L/6 hybridised to chromosome Bb8. Probes Bd4S/1-5 and Bd4L/6 hybridised to Br6, BAC clones Bd4L/7-10 mapped to chromosomes Br5. BAC clones Bd4L/6-8 and Bd4S/1 + Bd4S/5 + Bd4L/8 show chromosomal breakpoints in both Bb and Br subgenomes compared to the chromosomal fusion points in the genome Bd. In contrast to Bd genome, BAC clones Bd4S/3-5 show chromosomal breakpoint only in subgenome Bb and probes Bd4S/1 + CEN + Bd4L/10 show chromosomal breakpoint only in subgenome Br. Within BACs triplet Bd4S/1 + Bd4S/5 + Bd4L/8, probes Bd4S/1 and Bd4S/5 are mapped to the same chromosome arm of Br6, probes Bd4S/1 and Bd4L/8 are mapped to the opposite chromosome arms of Bb5. Within BACs triplets Bd1S/7 + Bd4S/1 + Bd4L/8 and Bd1S/7 + Bd4S/1 + Bd4S/4 and Bd1S/5 + Bd1S/7 + Bd4S/1, probes derived from interstitial part of the short arm of Bd1 and short arm of Bd4 mapped to the opposite arms of the chromosome Br6 indicating the presence of chromosomal fusion in contrast to genome Bd and subgenome Bb. Moreover, within BACs triplet Bd4S/4 + Bd4L/8 + Bd1L/8, probes derived from interstitial part of the long arm of Bd1 and long arm of Bd4 mapped to the opposite arms of the chromosome Br5 indicating the presence of chromosomal fusion in contrast to genome Bd and subgenome Bb.

Fig. S1

Fig. S2

Fig. S3
(a)

(b)

Fig. S4

Fig. S5

(a) *Brachypodium* nuclear diploid skeleton tree
(322 transcripts)

(b) *Brachypodium* plastid diploid skeleton tree
(31 transcripts)

Fig. S6

Fig. S7

Fig. S8

Fig. S9

Fig. S10

Fig. S11

Fig. S12

Fig. S13

Fig. S14

Fig. S15

Fig. S16

Fig. S17

